

IMHANS Newsletter

(Institute of Mental Health and Neurosciences, Kozhikode, Kerala)

Jan – June 2025

In Loving Memory of

DR. PADINHARATH KRISHNAKUMAR (1961 – 2025)

Dr. Padinharath Krishnakumar, the serving IMHANS Director, passed away on January 25, 2025, at the age of 63.

One of India's most respected figures in pediatric medicine and mental health, he had an extraordinary career that spanned over four decades, during which he helped shape the fields of child development, pediatrics, and mental health.

Dr. Krishnakumar's academic path was distinguished and purposeful. He earned his MBBS and DCH early in his career, and later went on to complete a DNB in Pediatrics and MD in Psychiatry—a rare combination that reflected his interdisciplinary approach to healthcare. His clinical and academic credentials were further recognized internationally with the award of FRCP (Glasgow).

As an educator and clinician, Dr. Krishnakumar began his career as Lecturer in Pediatrics under Department of Medical Education and finally retired as Professor of Pediatrics at Government Medical College, Thrissur. Also, he has been one of the longest serving Directors of IMHANS, joining in 2006 and working in that position till his death on January 25, 2025 (He retired from DME in 2023 but was later reappointed as Director considering his invaluable contributions to IMHANS).

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During his tenure, IMHANS became a nationally recognized mental health institution earmarked for development as a Centre of Excellence in Mental Health. IMHANS evolved into a postgraduate teaching and research centre affiliated to the KUHS. He established Child Development Services (CDS), and Centre for Interdisciplinary Brain Sciences (CIBS) at IMHANS. He was instrumental in starting NHM supported Community Mental Health programs in the four northern districts of Kerala which has later taken over by Health Services. An innovative mobile intervention program for children developed during this period in northern districts was subsequently adopted by the Govt. all over Kerala.

A prolific writer and speaker, Dr. Krishnakumar authored and co-authored more than 45 research papers in indexed journals, with numerous policy documents, and training manuals. He has published two books aiming to psychoeducate parents and general public regarding childhood developmental issues. He has also been a PhD guide recognized under KUHS and has guided more than 30 theses including PhD and MD theses. He was a member of academic council at Kerala University of Health Sciences, Thrissur and served as the chairman of Board of Studies in Rehabilitation Sciences under KUHS.

National Conference on Interventions for Indigenous populations: Tribal Mental Health Project of IMHANS in collaboration with Department of Psychosocial Support in Disaster Management, NIMHANS and Don Bosco College, Sulthan Bathery, organized 3-day National Conference *Innovations in Interventions for the indigenous Population* from 9th to 11th January at Sulthan Bathery.

Remembrance meeting for Dr Krishnakumar was held at Seminar Hall of IMHANS on 26th March 2025. The gathering included family, friends, and colleagues. Dr. KG. Sajeeth kumar (Principal, Govt. Medical College and Director in charge, IMHANS) delivered the Presidential address. Remembrance speeches were delivered by Dr Beena Philip (Mayor, Kozhikode), Sri Thottathil Ravindran (MLA, Kozhikode), P K Sreemathy Teacher (Former Health Minister), among others.

A souvenir album 'Meadows of Memories' compiled by IMHANS-Child Development Services was released at the remembrance meeting. The souvenir provided a photojournal of the modest beginnings of Child Development Services at Medical college campus under Dr Krishnakumar and the development of Centre of Excellence project.

Training programme on Geriatric Care & Dementia Care: IMHANS TeleManas team and Dept of Psychiatric Social Work collaborated for a series of training programmes on *Basic Geriatric and Dementia Care*, funded by National Institute of Social Defense (NISD). 14 programs were conducted between September 2024 to March 2025 with total of 357 participants from across the state.

Center for Interdisciplinary Brain Sciences (CIBS) at the Institute of Mental Health and Neurosciences, Kerala, initiated a research program on the genomics of childhood-onset psychosis funded by the Department of Biotechnology, Government of India. CIBS-IMHANS is a flagship research center established in 2022 to address fundamental and translational research questions in psychiatric and neurodevelopmental disorders.

CIBS collaborated with NIT, Kozhikode for publishing a review. S. Sreekumar, LA and RK. Ravindren, "Bridging the Gap: Cognitive Science Perspectives and Artificial Intelligence for Prediction and Detection of Specific Learning Disabilities," in IEEE Transactions on Cognitive and Developmental Systems. Link: <https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/document/10970751>

A Conclave on Clear Minds, Bright Futures: Uniting against drug abuse was organized jointly by Social Justice department Govt. of Kerala, IMHANS Tele-MANAS team, Access to Justice by All and District Administration Kozhikode, funded by Nasha Mukta Bharat Abhiyan. Legal professionals, Police officers and staff from Governmental depts underwent training and discussed legal aspects and mental health perspectives.

Workshop on Dialectical Behavior Therapy: Department of Clinical Psychology, IMHANS organized two-day workshop on *Dialectical Behavior Therapy (DBT)* on the 5th and 6th May 2025. Dr Keerthy Pai, Consultant Clinical Psychologist from Apolo Shine and Partner Element HPSS, Chennai conducted the workshop. 63 participants from all over Kerala attended the workshop.

Workshop on Psychodynamic Foundations: Department of Clinical Psychology in collaboration with Tele-MANAS organised a two days' Workshop on *Psychodynamic Foundations: Key Concepts and Practical Techniques* on 8th and 9th of April 2025. Mr. Mohammed Sadik, Psychology faculty from CIP, Ranchi conducted the workshop and was attended by 45 participants.

- ❖ Dr. Sajeeth Kumar K G, Director in-charge (Principal, Govt. Medical College, Calicut)
- ❖ Mr. Ramjith A R, Administrative Officer
- ❖ Dr Anton Paulson, Assistant Professor of Psychiatry
- ❖ Ms. Amrutha, PSW, RFU
- ❖ Mrs. Reshma T, PSW, CDS
- ❖ Ms. Fathimath Najiya, Laboratory Assistant Neurophysiology, CIBS

Tele-MANAS collaborated with various departments to organize programs during Sleep Awareness Week, World Hearing Day, National Safety Day, World Bipolar Day, International Women's Day, and World Parkinson's Day, International day against drug abuse and illicit trafficking, World Autism Awareness Day (with Autism Center).

Ente Keralam: IMHANS in collaboration with Tele-MANAS had organised a stall in the "Ente Keralam" exhibition at Kozhikode Beach, from 3rd to 12th May 2025. It was focused on creating public awareness on mental health and eradicating stigma in seeking support for mental health issues.

Published Manuals:

Updates on Clinical Services

- ❖ **Geriatric Clinic:** Geriatric Well Being sessions started. The sessions are conducted on every Tuesday at IMHANS. Geriatric mental health clinics are held on monthly basis in “Pakalveedu” at Kunduparamba in collaboration with Vayomithram programme by Kozhikode Corporation.
- ❖ **Child Development Services** conducted group therapy sessions for children with learning disabilities focusing on remedial education during the summer vacation. 378 children participated in the sessions over 2 months.
- ❖ **The Autism Center** funded by KSSM conducted a series of screening camps in Anganwadis and Tribal schools in Kozhikode and Wayanad district for early identification of developmental disorders. Six summer camps were conducted at IMHANS for beneficiaries in the month of April and May 2025. 67 children participated in these interactive camps.
- ❖ **Recovery Facilitation Project** funded by Social Justice department conducted an annual review of its effectiveness on 11th June 2025. The beneficiaries of the project and their family members participated.

Updates on Academics

- ❖ The 9th batch of M.Phil. Psychiatric Social Work students graduated from KUHS in the month of March.
- ❖ The 8th batch of Post Basic Diploma in Psychiatric Nursing students completed their course.
- ❖ The 5th batch of M.Phil. Clinical Psychology students graduated from KUHS in the month of March.
- ❖ 142 students from various parts of India, including central and state universities, completed their internship at IMHANS in the last 6 months. This included Masters students from Social Work (80), Psychology (70), and from the Bachelor of Audiology and Speech-Language Pathology (BASLP) (2) courses. Five graduate trainees completed internship in CIBS in last 6 months.